

Effects of Teachers' Participation in Decision Making on Academic Performance in English in Public Secondary Schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda

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Abstract: Background: The study sought to examine the effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda. The study used mixed research design.

Methods and Materials: The researcher used stratified random sampling to obtain the sample size of 109 teachers and head teachers determined by means of Yamane's formula. Questionnaires were administered to the respondents to collect data. Descriptive statistics, correlational analysis, and linear regression model of analysis were utilized to analyze data. Quantitative data from closed questions was analyzed using descriptive statistics through Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software version 26.0.

Results: The findings showed significant effects of the involvement of teachers in taking decisions on academic performance in English. The results of data analysis presented that the relationship between teachers' participation in decision-making and academic performance in English among public secondary students was .910** while the R Square was .828. Clearly, 82.8% of all variables of academic performance can be explained by one of all variables of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools. The variables were statistically significant with regression mean square of 63.270 and residual mean square was .123 while $F=514.007$ and $P\text{-value} = .000^b$.

Conclusion: The study concluded that there was a significant relationship between teachers' participation in decision-making and academic performance in English among public secondary students in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda and teachers' active involvement in decision making significantly affects academic attainment. Researcher recommends schools' administration and educational policy makers to adopt participatory decision-making approach and closely collaborate with teachers in decision making to maximize academic performance in all subjects apart from English.

Keywords: Teachers' Participation, decision making, academic performance, English in Public Secondary Schools, Nyamagabe District.

I. INTRODUCTION

Academic performance is a central indicator of effectiveness within an educational institution. It indicates the quality of education offered in such a school. The place of educators in effective academic attainment is irreplaceable. Teachers are the cornerstone of schools. Students' academic achievement is the burning issue within developing countries including Rwanda. The teaching quality is believed to enhance economic development in Rwanda and is a critical element contributing to the upgraded academic attainment among students (Carter, Leonard, Onwuegbuzie, Rose, & Sabates, 2021). Achieving a good academic performance in a school needs active participation of teachers in making relevant decisions. A number of studies addressed the golden place of the participation of teachers in decision making in academic context. The

participation of educators in decision making is believed to foster academic achievement among students. Haryanto (2020) and Ahmed, Samina and Ahmed (2019) assert that the participation of educators in decision making enhances academic attainment among students in addition to boosting the school's effectiveness as a whole. Haryanto (2020) realized that the involvement of teachers in academic matters has an influence on the motivation of teachers and the higher achievement in public secondary schools in Nigeria. Teachers involved in making academic decisions feel a sense of accountability and commitment to such decisions. Tijani (2020) equally noted that participative and consultative decision making processes heighten school effectiveness in all aspects of school management. Educators are, hereby, active contributors to decisions and key implementers of the same decisions.

Another study conducted by Marakis (2021) in Mombasa illustrated that teachers' participation in decision making affects all angles of school life and teachers feel engaged in their attributions. In their study, Macha and Mahgma (2022) realized that the participation of teachers in making decisions related to academic issues raises teachers' efficacy and commitment to a successful implementation of the decisions in Meru District in Tanzania. Other scholars state that increased teacher's involvement in school's decision making process is significantly important because those closest to the children can contribute fruitfully towards providing high quality services to students and the school community and they are accountable for the decisions (Migambi, 2018; Samech, 2010 & Bauer, 1992). The teacher is clearly the leading instrument to bring forth preferred improved learning outcomes (MINEDUC, 2024, MINEDUC, 2007). Educators are the cornerstones of the learning institution. Therefore, their involvement in making pertinent decisions leads to great academic achievements in various subjects. Following different reforms in Rwandan education system, English language has taken the central part as a medium of instructions since 2008 (Serge, Oyebimpe & Andala, 2021) onwards. Nonetheless, academic performance is still poor in Rwandan schools (NESA, 2022). Studies on the effects of teachers' participation in decision-making on academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Rwanda are scarce. Therefore, this study sought to examine the effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in English in Nyamagabe District. It was guided by the following specific objectives:

- i. To assess the level of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda
- ii. To assess the level of academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda that is due to the participation of teachers in decision making
- iii. To determine the effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The researcher conducted the present study relying on two theories notably participatory decision-making theory and Social Cognitive Theory (SCT), proposed by Albert Bandura.

Participatory Decision Making Theory

Participatory decision-making theory puts forward the place of shared leadership by involving teachers in decision making and it is the key indicator of distributed leadership practices (Hodaya & Berkovich, 2021) in a school or any other institution. Educators feel a sense of decision ownership and commitment to implement successfully the decisions taken together. All stakeholders enjoy shared responsibility in making decisions and they remain faithful to them. Pashiards (2014) advocates for the integration of participatory decision-making theory in schools. Gafni et al. (1997) believed that shared decision-making approach brings together all educational stakeholders and they work collaboratively to meet the goals with excellence.

Hence, the school leaders are required to enhance group decision quality in order to direct the school towards educational effectiveness whose indicators include the students' academic achievements (Swamalatha, 2016).

Participatory decision-making model facilitated the researcher to examine the effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in English, to assess the level of participation and identify the effects of teacher participation in decision making on academic performance among others as discussed in chapter four and five. Given the fact that shared decision making model is recognized in South African Act 84 of 2010 in schools and three years later the model was recognized in Basic Education Act of 2013 in Kenya (Migambi, 2018), the scholar trusted the unprecedented value of participatory decision making in schools to shape learners' academic performance and the overall school's success.

Therefore, participatory decision making can enhance the level of participation in taking decisions and then shape academic attainment among students in one way or another as the findings demonstrated.

Social Cognitive Theory

Correspondingly, the researcher considered Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) in this study since there can be a number of factors that can influence decision making and academic performance in schools. SCT emphasizes the reciprocal relationship between personal factors, environmental factors, and behavior factors. It has been applied to understand how teachers' participation in decision-making processes can influence academic achievement in English in public high schools in Rwanda. According to SCT theorists, individuals acquire some knowledge while interacting with others in a societal setting and they adopt behavior of others from observation (Razieh & Muhammad, 2011). To say it otherwise, SCT (also referred to as SCLT) involves imitation and the reproduction of observed behavior as per Bandura (1977). It is understandable that this theory bases on the principles of imitation, observation and modelling.

Therefore, the theory is applicable in the current study to understand the way teachers' participation in decision-making processes can influence academic performance in English. From the standpoint of the study, the model helps us to examine personal factors such as teachers' belief, self-efficacy, and attitudes which shape their behavior and instructional practices. This is to say that involvement in decision-making can enhance teachers' self-efficacy in teaching English, their beliefs about the importance of student voice and autonomy, or their attitudes towards using student-centered instructional strategies in English classrooms.

As far as Environment factors and behavior are concerned, the implication of SCLT in this study is that it facilitated to explore how supportive school climates or environment, organizational factors, collaborative professional cultures, and inclusive decision-making processes can influence teachers' instructional practices and their ability to promote academic performance in English positively or negatively. Similarly, the theory supported to examine how teachers' participation in decision-making shapes their choice of instructional approaches, curriculum design, assessment methods, and interventions in English classrooms since they reflect teachers' behavior within instructional context.

SCLT is likely to promote self-regulation which results in rewarding oneself after meeting the desired goal or behavior (Bandura, 1978). Sincerely speaking, this actual theory is associated to the unprecedented value of teachers' participation in making decisions in which the teacher's presence is felt and they can be held accountable for the taken decisions. The spirit of decision ownership develops positively.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The figure 1 below demonstrates the conceptual framework by indicating an interconnectedness amid independent variable and dependent variable as affected by extraneous variables in different aspects.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

The figure 1 labeled conceptual framework gives an image of the association between independent variables (teachers' participation in decision-making) and the dependent variable (academic performance in English). However, both independent variable and the dependent one can be affected by intervening variables. From independent variables the researcher identifies sub-themes to show some academic tasks to which instructors can contribute to make meaningful decisions.

Teaching and learning management, class size selection, the promotion procedures, and the management of students' discipline fall under independent variable and can influence academic performance differently. These variables may allow teachers to participate in decision making process for the good of the effectiveness of learning institution and the students' academic achievement. Similarly, the sub-themes such as improved language skills development, success rate or test score, promotion rate are categorized under dependent variables.

Nonetheless, the place of intervening variables or extraneous variables notably teacher's educational level and teaching experience, the school environment is worth mentioning. They moderate participation in decision making and academic performance in English in one way or another. They can affect the way educators are involved in taking decision including academic achievements in English in public secondary schools. Teacher's educational level and their experiences comprise the characteristics of the teacher which encourages or discourages his or her participation in decision making. Respectively, the school's environment plays a significant role in participatory decision making and academic achievement. Briefly, figure 2.1 displays this kind of interconnectedness among discussed variables.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Kumar (2011), expounds a research design as a practical plan that the researcher adapts to solve the research questions validly, impartially, precisely and cautiously. It gives an understanding of the research problem also. A study design known as the strategies of inquiry is a type of inquiry within qualitative methods, quantitative methods and mixed methods approaches that grant specific directions for procedures in a research. There are three popular types of research designs. While qualitative research design is concerned with an exploration and understanding of the meaning attributed to human problem, quantitative research design deals with testing theories by analyzing the relationship amongst variables (Cresswell, 2009). This strategy measures the variables quantitatively then analyze them statistically. Contrarily, mixed research design uses the combination of both quantitative design and qualitatively. Both approaches are used simultaneously so as to achieve an excellent quality study.

The researcher utilized mixed research design known as descriptive research design. It is the best way to bring forth valid and reliable results. Sharon (2004) confirms that this multiple methods approach can produce precision, accuracy and clarity to the object of analysis. Cresswell and Cresswell (2018) equally state that using mixed methods is fruitful in the sense that it provides the best understanding of the research problem, opens doors to multiple methods, different epistemology and assumptions and various tools for collecting and analyzing required data in reference to pragmatic world view.

Cresswell (2009) asserts that mixed research design stands many chance to be applied since pragmatism paradigm permits the researcher to use pluralistic strategies in order to understand deeply the problem under study. Correspondingly, various methods can be used to collect and analyze data. In this context, concurrent triangulation mixed methods have been particularly used to collect quantitative data and qualitative one at the same time and thereof integrate them into the interpretation of the overall findings. Concurrent triangulation mixed method obliges the simultaneous analysis of two types of the results and allows comparison of both types of data to decide whether there exists convergence, difference or a combination of both (Cresswell, 2009).

Shortly, concurrent triangulation strategy is very important in this study since it has allowed the collection of both qualitative data and quantitative information simultaneously. Hence, its being cross-sectional in nature saved the time unlike longitudinal nature. The study provided meaningful description of the impact resulting from participation of teachers in taking decisions on the academic achievement in English in high schools. consequently, collected data gave an understanding of the effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in English specifically within governmental high schools in Rwanda.

Target Population

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), population is the total collection of individuals, events or items with shared noticeable characteristics. In addition, they assert that a research would like to generalize the findings to target population referred to as absolute population. The present study targeted 150 secondary teachers including secondary head teachers from the public schools mainly G.S Kaduha, G.S Maso, G.S Nyamiyaga, G.S Musenyi, G.S Kinyana, G.S Turyango, G.S Mutakara, G.S Mubuga, G.S Kibumbwe and E.S Kaduha. Teachers, generally, play a key role in shaping academic performance especially in English required of students. Decisions that teachers make in their profession affect students directly or indirectly. Correspondingly, the school principals as the top managers of an educational institution play a vital role in shaping the academic performance apart from their overall duties to direct the school to effectiveness and efficiency through their daily leadership over the school. Besides, the school principals are the central players to promote teacher participation in decision making and empower them with required competences for fruitful decision making. Therefore, conducting a study on this population highlighted impact of involving tutors or educators in taking decisions on academic achievement specifically in English in public secondary schools in Rwanda.

Table 1: Target Population

Groups	Total
Secondary teachers	140
Secondary head teachers	10
Total	150

Source: Primary Data, 2024

Sample Design

The study used probability sampling rather than purposive sampling design. This sampling design has given equal opportunities to the respondents to be eligible in the study. Probability sampling stands a great chance to employ successfully test of statistical significance that allow inferences to be made about the population from which the sample size is drawn. In this regard, stratified random sampling was preferably useful to establish a representation of every variable characterizing the respondents. Stratified sampling ascertains that every strata or variable such as gender, education level, age, experience, cultural differences and more is represented proportionally (Kabiru & Njenga, 2009; Cresswell, 2009). Consequently, sampling error has been reduced since the respondents with similar characteristics have been considered.

Sample Size

Following the type of current study, the investigator applied Yamane method of 1967 which is $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$ to decide the sample size that has been generalized later to the entire population.

Whereby n stands for a sample; N represents the population size then e means the margin of error.

Reference to Yamane's simplified formula, there is 95% level of confidence which gives 0.95 level of precision. Hence, the sample size was calculated in each school:

$$e=1-0.95 =0.05$$

$$N=150$$

Using this formula, I have taken the target population size of 150 and the margin of error equivalent to 0.05 which gives a sample size of 109. The sample size is greater than 50%. Therefore, it is in the acceptable range of the sample as Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) suggest. The sample size of 109 ascertains that the mean converged the standard deviation since it is above 50% of the target population.

Hazelrigg (2004) equally supports the use of a larger sample size: "the larger the sample drawn from a population, the more likely (\bar{X}) converges μ . This is to say that the greater the sample size surpasses 50%, the much more confident that the mean converges the standard deviation. The table 3.2 below sums up this sample size.

Sampling Techniques

Studies had put in place forms of sampling strategies in research notably random sampling and non-probability sampling referred to as purposive sampling. Reference to Bryman (2012), probability sampling stands a great chance to employ successfully test of statistical significance that allow inferences to be made about the population from which the sample is taken. The researcher adopted probability sampling since this strategy gives every informant an equal opportunity to participate in the study.

Probability sampling is divided into different types like simple random sampling, systematic sampling (or multiple/ double repetitive sampling), multistage sampling, stratified sampling and cluster sampling. Each strategy has its own merits and demerits. The researcher preferred stratified sampling to others. "The goal of stratified random sampling is to achieve desired representation from various subgroups in the population". Besides, stratified sampling ascertains that every strata or variable such as gender, education level, age, experience, cultural differences and more is represented proportionally (Kabiru & Njenga, 2009; Cresswell, 2009). Stratification ensures the meaningful representation of the definite characteristics of individuals since each one has been reflected consistently.

Data Collection Methods

Data Collection Instruments

Considering the nature of concurrent mixed method, the researcher used questionnaires to gather primary data firstly. Setting both closed-ended and open-ended questions has been of paramount values in terms of providing statistical data and qualitative data (Cresswell, 2009) as well in relation to the effects that involving instructors in decision making in secondary school can have on the academic achievement in English in public secondary schools. Besides, questionnaires are good since the target population is literate. Similarly, administering questionnaires is less time consuming compared to interviewing the whole respondents. Questionnaires are useful tools. They can provide coherent statistical raw data apart from being easy to reach many individuals. Questionnaires are also good to protect the privacy of informants. A questionnaire enables participants to answer with honest since it hides their identity and individual privacy is sustained (Roopa & Rani, 2012). Individual privacy assures respondents with safety and confidentiality of provided information as ethical consideration obliges. Nonetheless, questionnaires have drawbacks to be aware of especially when they are poorly designed (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003).

Secondly, the scholar considered document analysis to enrich knowledge construction. Some available records were analyzed in accordance with the present study in order to provide quality knowledge from different perspectives. The scholar consulted books, scholarly articles and government documents so as to deepen understanding and relate the previous studies to Rwandan context today. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) argue that the aforesaid documents are good sources of literatures while carrying out a study. By consulting different documents, the researcher was able to clarify the problem and recommend the ways forward. Thirdly, the researcher employed the structured review of records in the form of checklist for the available school information while collecting data.

V. FINDINGS

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

This study analyzed the demographic characteristics of respondents; this information was a baseline statistic to the research findings. The demographic characteristics were gender, working experience, and education level. The results for such socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents were presented in the tables below.

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Male	74	67.9
	Female	35	32.1
	Total	109	100.0

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

Table 2 shows gender distribution of respondents. Male respondents occupy 67.9% while the female respondents were 32.1%. This implies that the majorities of the respondents were males.

Level of teachers' Participation in Decision Making in Public Secondary Schools

The first objective was to assess the level of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda. The results were presented and interpreted.

Figure 2: Level of Teachers' Participation in Decision Making In the School

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

Figure 2 presents the results about the level of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda. The findings demonstrated that 42.39% of the respondents responded that they had high participation while 67.61% responded that they had very high level of participation in decision making.

Table 3: Level of Teachers' Participation in Decision Making In Public Secondary Schools

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Not Sure		Agree		Strongly Agree		Total	Mean	Sd
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
Teachers are involved in teaching and learning resource management	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	31.2	75	68.8	109	4.69	.465
Teachers participate in the determination of the class size	0	0	11	10.1	60	55.0	38	34.9	0	0	109	3.25	.626
Teachers are involved in promotion procedures of students	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	28.4	78	71.6	109	4.72	.453
Teachers participate in the management of the discipline of students	0	0	0	0	0	0	48	44.0	61	56.0	109	4.56	4.99
Overall Mean											4.305		

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

Table 3 presents the results of the first objective of this study of assessing the level of teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda. Regarding whether teachers were involved in teaching and learning resource management, 31.2% agreed and 68.8% strongly agreed that they were involved in teaching and learning resource management. Whether teachers participated in the determination of the class size, 10.1% disagreed while 55.0% were not sure. Contrarily to that, 34.9% of the respondents agreed that teachers participated in the determination of the class size while teachers who were involved in promotion procedures of students, 28.4% agreed and 71.6% strongly agreed that teachers were involved in promotion procedures of students. Concerning that teachers participated in the management of the discipline of students, 44.0% agreed and 56.0% strongly agreed that teachers participate in the management of the discipline of students. The overall mean was 4.305 which was between agree (3) and strongly agree (4). This indicated that there was significant teachers' participation in decision making in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda.

Level of Academic Performance in English in Public Secondary Schools

The second objective was to assess the level of academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Rwanda that is due to the participation of teachers in decision-making. The results are below.

Table 4: Level of Academic Performance In English In Public Secondary Schools

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Not Sure		Agree		Strongly Agree		Total	Mean	Sd
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
Academic performance in English is very high	0	0	0	0	27	24.8	72	66.1	10	9.2	109	3.84	.564
Academic performance is high	0	0	0	0	15	13.8	56	51.4	38	34.9	109	4.21	.668
Academic performance in English is low	0	0	68	62.4	20	18.3	21	19.3	0	0	109	2.57	.798
Academic performance in English very low	21	19.3	88	80.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	109	1.81	3.96
Overall Mean												3.107	

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

Table 4 presents the results regarding the level of academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda that is due to the participation of teachers in decision making. Regarding the level of academic performance in English 24.8% of the respondents were not sure, 66.1% agreed and 9.2% strongly agreed that academic performance in English was very high. Whether academic performance was high, the percentage of 13.8% were not sure, 51.4% agreed, and 34.9% strongly agreed that academic performance was high. The percentage of 19.3 believed that academic performance in English was low. The overall mean was 3.107 that was between agree (3) and strongly agree (4) presented that there was significant level of academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe, Rwanda that is due to the participation of teachers in decision making.

Effects of Teachers' Participation In Decision Making On Academic Performance In English In Public Secondary Schools

The third objective was to determine the effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Rwanda as presented below.

Table 5: Effects of Teachers' Participation in Decision Making On Academic Performance In English In Public Secondary Schools

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Not Sure		Agree		Strongly Agree		Total	Mean	Sd
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
Improved language skills have been due to the participation of teachers in decision making	0	0	0	0	0	0	64	58.7	45	41.3	109	4.41	.495
Test score and success rate of learners increased due to participation of teachers in decision making	0	0	0	0	0	0	78	71.6	31	28.4	109	4.28	.453
Teachers' participation in decision making increased promotion rate of learners	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	38.5	67	61.5	109	4.61	.489
School attendance and self-esteem increased because of teachers' participation in decision making	0	0	0	0	0	0	89	81.7	20	18.3	109	4.18	3.89
Overall Mean												4.37	

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

Table 5 presents the results determining the effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda. Whether improved language skills had been due to the participation of teachers in decision making, 58.7% agreed and 41.3% strongly agreed. Regarding the test score and success rate of learners that was increased due to the participation of teachers in decision making, 71.6% agreed and 28.4% strongly agreed. Concerning whether teachers' participation in decision making increased promotion rate of learners, 38.5%

agreed and 61.5% strongly agreed that teachers' participation in decision making increased promotion rate of learners. Besides, 81.7% agreed and 18.3% strongly agreed that school attendance and self-esteem increased because of teachers' participation in decision making. The overall mean of 4.37 between agree (3) and strongly agree (4) presented that there were significant effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in English in public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda.

Table 6: Correlation between Teachers' Participation in Decision Making and Academic Performance

		Level of teachers' participation decision making	Level of academic inperformance
Level of teachers' participation in decision making	Pearson Correlation	1	.910**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	109	109
Level of academic performance	Pearson Correlation	.910**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	109	109

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

Table 6 shows the correlation between the teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance as per Pearson coefficients. Normally, the Pearson coefficients relationship are between -1 to 1 whereby -1 to 0 points negative relationship and 0 to 1 points positive relationship. From -1 to -0.5 marks high negative & from -0.5 to 0 marks low negative relationship, and from 0 to 0.5 presents low positive, from 0.5 to 1 presents high positive relationship. The outputs of data analysis presented that the relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance in English was .910** which indicated that there was a statistically significant relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance in English among public secondary students in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda.

Table 7: Model Summary of Teachers' Participation in Decision Making and Academic Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.910 ^a	.828	.826	.351

a. Predictors: (Constant), Level of teachers' participation in decision making

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

Table 7 presents the results on the overall model's significance of teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance and the R Square was .828. The study clarified that 82.8% of all variables of academic performance can be explained by one of all variables of teachers' participation in decision making among public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda. The standard error of coefficients was 0.351 which was not very high.

Table 8: ANOVA^a of Teachers' Participation in Decision Making on Academic Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	63.270	1	63.270	514.007	.000 ^b
	Residual	13.171	107	.123		
	Total	76.440	108			

a. Dependent Variable: Level of academic performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Level of teachers' participation in decision making

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

Table 8 presents the analysis of variance of teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance in English. The results presented that the variables were statistically significant with regression mean square of 63.270 and residual

mean square was .123 while $F=514.007$ and $P\text{-value}=.000^b$, which confirmed that there was a significant relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance in English among public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda. Mean square and residual mean square present the mean squared differences within academic performance and this is a components of F used to test for differences between variables or is the estimate of the variance of the errors that help to determine the variation in the data that is not accounted for by the teachers' participation in decision making in the model.

Table 9: Coefficients^a of Teachers' Participation in Decision Making and Academic Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	.867	.157	5.529	.000	.556	1.178
1 Level of teachers' participation in decision making	.834	.037	.910	22.672	.000	.761 .907

a. Dependent Variable: Level of academic performance

Source: Primary Data, (2024)

Table 9 presents the constant coefficients of independent and dependent variables of teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance in English. The overall constant results with $P\text{ value}=.000$ showed that there was a significant relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance in English among public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda.

VI. CONCLUSION

The research concluded that the participation of teachers in decision making affects academic performance in English after examining the effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in the public secondary schools in Nyamagabe District. Both the level of teachers' participation in decision making and the level of academic performance in English are significant as indicated by the findings. In conclusion, there were significant effects of teachers' participation in decision making on academic performance in English in public secondary schools. The outputs of data analysis presented that the relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance in English among public secondary students was $.910^{**}$ which concluded that there was a significant relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and academic performance in English among public secondary students in Nyamagabe District, Rwanda.

Therefore, there was a need to adopt participatory decision making style in schools so as to maximize the academic achievement and teachers' accountability towards the decision. Researcher recommends schools' administration and educational policy makers to adopt participatory decision making approach and closely collaborate with teachers in decision making so as to maximize academic performance in all subjects apart from English in Rwanda.

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